

Model-based Scale-Up Design of Rotating Packed Beds for CO₂ Capture: An Iterative Methodology and Examination of Operational Parameters

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ABSTRACT

Effectively scaling up the Rotating Packed Bed (RPB) absorption process is pivotal for the advancement of solvent-based CO₂ capture technology. However, existing models are primarily focused on lab-scale and pilot plant absorbers, neglecting the impact of key operational parameters on RPB design. The complexity and non-linearity inherent in scaling up a lab-scale RPB configuration present significant challenges. This study addresses these gaps by introducing a comprehensive scale-up design methodology for RPB absorbers using monoethanolamine (MEA) as the solvent. The approach is grounded in a custom model based on first principles and uses the shooting method to solve material and energy balance equations. This model is generic and independent of commercial software and is specifically designed to examine the scale-up and operational behaviors of an RPB. To validate CO₂ capture accuracy, this model is extensively compared with experimental data from MEA-based RPB studies. The proposed model outlines a detailed design procedure, featuring representative correlations for estimating inner diameter and axial length. An iterative methodology is adopted to meet CO₂ capture specifications, culminating in the determination of an optimal outer diameter. Importantly, the model enables extensive analysis of key operational parameters such as rotating speed, liquid-to-gas ratio, and liquid temperature, and their impacts on RPB design. The findings underscore the liquid-to-gas ratio as the most influential factor in the design process. In conclusion, this study offers a robust tool for enhancing CO₂ capture in RPB applications. By exploring key operational parameters and scale-up processes, it advances low-carbon technologies and contributes to a more sustainable future.

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